

How-To: Citing Critical Artifacts

You are likely here because you are submitting a non-peer reviewed item to a general repository such as Zenodo. It is proper research practice to cite the artifacts that were the most critical for the work, including the data and software ([Starr et al. 2015](#); [Katz et al. 2021](#)). Citing these artifacts gives credit to those that created those artifacts, positively impacts retention rates of technical talent in our field, and helps funders determine the impact of those artifacts for potential future funding. This how-to will guide you through determining the critical artifacts to cite and how to cite them properly to ensure your citation is counted ([Stall et al. 2023](#)). So, take a few moments to review the section most relevant to you and give your fellow researchers a nod of thanks with a proper citation to the work that helped you the most.

What artifacts to cite in various scenarios are listed in section 1. Instructions on how to properly cite these artifacts are in section 2. The expected workflow is for you to determine what artifacts you should cite based on the type of artifact you are submitting by using section 1, then use section 2 to determine what information to gather for each item to be cited and where to add that information.

1. What “Critical Artifacts” Should I Cite?

Critical artifacts are the data, software, publications, presentations, posters, and other research artifacts that were the most important to understanding the result or discussion in your work. What is critical looks different for each type of resource, so examples are included in subsections below for each submitted major resource type.

The scenarios included in this document typically focus on scenarios where citations to data and software are recommended. These scenarios also recommend a citation to the reference publication for the data or software. Reference publications are peer-reviewed publications the data or software authors wrote describing the data or software. When these exist, they must *always* be cited in addition to the data or software used. You can typically find information on these publications in the documentation or description of the dataset or software artifact. In some cases, there is an ideal order to use when submitting your artifacts to make citing other artifacts easier. The general rule is to submit your custom dataset or software in the same order they are used in your workflow.

The bulleted lists below show the artifacts to cite in each scenario and the ideal artifact submission order in the more complex examples. Instructions on how to cite these items are in section 2.

1.1 Datasets

This section is for researchers interested in submitting datasets to a repository, including generalist repositories (e.g., Zenodo) and domain-specific repositories. Please note that GitHub,

GitLab, and similar websites are not acceptable repositories because users can delete the hosted resources. Also, DOIs minted through the GitHub-Zenodo workflow are categorized as software, which is incorrect for datasets and makes discovery more difficult. If this path is used, you will need to manually change the DOI type to “Dataset” through Zenodo’s interface. Otherwise, direct submission of datasets to a permanent repository, such as Zenodo, is preferred.

Datasets are typically generated either by observation, software, or the combination of both. All three possibilities are covered by the examples in this section with increasing complexity.

A. Observational dataset created with only common software (e.g., Excel)

- (Common software such as Excel are not typically cited.)
- Cite the instruments or sensors used to perform the measurements.
- Cite any important publications resulting from or describing the work.

B. Dataset generated by software with no input data

- Cite the version of the software(s), such as simulations or processing software, used to generate the data.
- If relevant, cite the version of the main software(s) used to perform analysis of the generated dataset. If a custom script was created for this purpose, cite the version used.
- Cite the reference publications for each software cited, if available.
- Include all settings given to the software to generate the data in the description of the dataset.
- Cite any important publications for the work.

Artifact submission order:

1. All custom analysis software developed.
2. Datasets produced by pre-existing software.
3. Datasets generated by the custom analysis software.

C. Dataset produced by software with input data

- Cite the version of the data as provided by the data repository for each input dataset.
- Cite the version of the software(s) used to generate the data, such as simulations or processing software.
- Cite the version of each custom dataset generated by the software and used in the work.
- Cite the version of the main software(s) used to perform the analysis of the generated dataset. If a custom script was created for this purpose, cite the version used.
- Cite the reference publications for each dataset and software cited, if available.
- Include all settings given to the software to generate the data in the description of the dataset.
- Cite any important publications for the work.

Artifact submission order:

1. All custom analysis software developed.
2. Datasets produced by pre-existing software.
3. Datasets generated by the custom analysis software.

1.2 Software

This section is for researchers interested in submitting software to a repository, including generalist repositories (e.g., Zenodo) and domain-specific repositories. Please note that GitHub, GitLab, and similar websites are not acceptable repositories because users can delete the hosted resources.

The impact of software developed for use in science is typically either single-use software, limited-use software, or widely used software (see below). The basic rule of thumb is the wider the intended impact for the software, both in application and community usage, the more the dependencies of the software must be cited, including any required compilers. The three scenarios below cover these categories in increasing order.

- *Single-Use Software*: Typically a script or code developed in support of a peer-reviewed research publication.
- *Limited-Use Software*: Software intended for use within a single research group or for a specific research topic.
- *Wide-Use Software*: Publicly available software designed for use across multiple research groups and science areas, typically with software engineering best practices implemented.

For more mature software, more than one version of a given dependency is often supported. In those cases, it is best practice to cite the concept DOI of the dependency that is supported by the software for simplicity.

Pro tip: Often, the calling method in the software does not indicate the version of the dependencies, but the details of the software environment can provide this information (e.g., “conda list” commands for python software).

A. One-time use script supporting a publication

- Cite the version of the **key** software dependencies used, typically those directly called in the script.
- If a compiler or interpreter for the script is required, then cite the version used.

B. Limited use software

- Cite the versions used for the **key** software dependencies **plus** all the dependencies used substantially in the work.
- If a compiler or interpreter for the software is required, then cite the version used.

C. Wide use software

- Cite the general software used for **all** of the software dependencies. Include the date on which support for the versions of the software dependencies was last tested.
- If a compiler or interpreter for the software is required, then cite the versions supported.

1.3 Presentations, posters, reports and peer-reviewed publications

This section is for researchers interested in submitting a presentation, poster, reports including conference reports, or publication preprints to a repository, including generalist repositories (e.g., Zenodo) and domain-specific repositories. The recommendations below also generally apply to peer-reviewed publications, but you should consult the journal for the details on how to cite artifacts in those publications. In those cases, make sure to follow all journal-specific citation instructions. Please note that GitHub, GitLab, and similar websites are not acceptable repositories because users can delete the hosted resources.

If one of the main topics of the artifact describes a result depending on a dataset, software, or similar artifact, then the version of the artifact used should be cited in the metadata. A few common scenarios follow.

A. Analyzing or Comparing Datasets

- Cite the version of the data as provided by the data repository for each dataset analyzed or included in the comparison.
- Cite the version of the **main** software(s) used to perform the analysis or comparison. If a custom script was created for this purpose, cite the version used.
- Cite the version used for each custom dataset produced by the analysis or comparison.
- Cite the version of the software(s) used to generate any data used, such as simulations or processing software.
- Cite the reference publications for each dataset and software cited, if available.
- Include all settings given to the software to generate the data in the description of the dataset.
- Cite any important publications for the work.

Artifact submission order:

1. All custom analysis software.
2. Datasets produced by the main software.
3. Datasets generated by the custom analysis software.

B. Progress report on ongoing development for data or software not ready for a DOI

- Cite the version of the dataset or software used.

- Cite any important publications for the work.

C. Conference report

- Cite all presentations and posters presented at the conference.
- If relevant, cite the URL of dedicated OSF, Zenodo, or similar community where conference materials were submitted.
- Cite any important publications for the work.

Artifact submission order:

1. All presentations and posters presented at the conference.
2. The conference report.

2. How Do I Cite Them?

2.1 What is a citation?

A citation is a way to acknowledge that the cited artifact significantly influenced the work. For example, the artifacts typically cited in peer-reviewed publications are other publications, usually those that are relevant to the history of the topic, the methods used, or results that are compared to those presented. An example of a correct software citation is below, copied from Stall et al. (2023). Correct data and software citations include the same information.

Shumate, A. (2022). agshumate/LiftoffTools: (v0.4.3.2) [Computer software]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6967163>

The necessary parts of a citation are the authors (A. Shumate in this case), the publication year (2022), the name of the artifact (agshumate/LiftoffTools), the version (v0.4.3.2), the type of artifact (Computer software), the publisher (Zenodo), and the identifier (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6967163>). Citation formatting requirements vary per journal and repository. Numerous formats of artifact citations with DOIs can be easily obtained through the CrossCite service available at citation.doi.org.

2.2 Which identifier is best?

Once you have determined which artifacts need to be cited, you will need to retrieve the most appropriate identifier out of the available options to form a correct citation. As a default, the version specific DOIs are the best choice for citing any resource.

If that DOI is not available or the recommendations above state otherwise, the DOI associated with the overall object, or the “concept DOI” as on Zenodo, is sufficient. In that case, make sure to include the access date for that resource in your item’s description. The screenshot below shows the difference between the two types of DOIs on Zenodo. Please see the appendix for instructions on how to cite an item when a DOI is not available. If the item is a custom dataset or

script, then the best practice is to create a version-specific DOI for the item through a generalist repository, such as Zenodo. If the item is too large for Zenodo or the generalist repository chosen, then contact the most relevant domain-specific or institution-specific repository for potential archival support.

Screenshot from a landing page on Zenodo showing the difference between the version-specific DOI and the “Concept” DOI.

Creating DOIs for software is an increasing trend, so it is still likely to need to cite software that does not have a DOI. In these cases, Software Heritage Identifiers (SWHID) for the relevant software version should be retrieved if possible. To search for Software Heritage Identifiers (SWHIDs), go to <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/>. Creation and retrieval instructions are available at <https://www.softwareheritage.org/how-to-archive-reference-code/>.

2.3 Making your citation count

Citations recorded in a description or in the files of the submission are not counted by existing pipelines external to publishers, meaning that the authors of the artifact you cite will not receive credit for the citation if it is only in those places. Citations must be correctly included in the metadata of the item to take advantage of the existing infrastructure pipelines. Publishers have collaboratively created substantial infrastructure to streamline this process. If your submission type is a preprint or a peer-reviewed publication, you should skip this subsection and consult the journal for the details on how to cite artifacts in those publications. In those cases, make sure to follow all journal-specific citation instructions.

For submissions to Zenodo, the recommended citations should be entered in the “Related Works” section on the Zenodo submission page. Each citation requires four pieces of information: the Relation, the Identifier, the Scheme, and the Resource type.

Related works

Related works

Specify identifiers of related works. Supported identifiers include DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTC, URNs, and URLs.

Relation * Identifier * Scheme * Resource type *

Select relation...

Add related work

The “Related works” section on the Zenodo submission page.

- *Relation*: In most cases, the relation “Cites” is the best choice. Important exceptions are indicated in the table below.

Table 2: Relation types for specialized cases

Submitted Artifact Type	Relation Entry	Cited Artifact
Reference publication for data or software	“Describes”	Data or software that is the primary topic of the publication
Data or software	“Cite with” (“Is described by” if NA)	Reference publication for that data or software
Data	“Is output of” (“Is derived from” if NA)	Software used to generate the data
Data	“Is derived from”	Input data
Software	“Requires”	Software dependencies
Software	“Is compiled by”	Supported compilers

- *Identifier*: The preferred identifier should be entered in this field, e.g., <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17613136> as an example DOI or “swh:1:dir:f435d21dbd63032ea805e73c87981e646c18d6b3;origin=https://github.com/EnsembleGovServices/kamodo-dashboard;visit=swh:1:snp:f9d021fc83d30d046a2387b3619383f4cb5a7d30;anchor=swh:1:rev:7a86773fa981d4e5a2ce2dc8a6f394d09fbfc0e9” as an example SWHID, or <https://github.com/sunpy/sunpy> as an example URL.
- *Scheme*: The scheme or identifier type should be selected here from the dropdown list to match the identifier entered in the previous field (e.g., “DOI” for DOIs). If a SWHID is

used, then “Other” should be selected. If only a URL is available, select the “URL” option.

- *Resource type*: The type of resource the identifier references should be entered here. The resource type closest to the cited resource should be selected from the dropdown list.

To add additional related works, click the *Add related work* button.

Appendix

In non-ideal cases, a DOI or other globally unique persistent identifier is not available for a data or software resource. In these cases, the URL to the main branch of the publicly available data or software repository should be used so that others can see what was used to produce the given product or result. If the data or software is not public, then a link to a website where access can be requested should be included in the citation metadata. Add the access date to your description field to help others understand any differences between your result and their efforts at a later date.

References

- Katz D.S., Chue Hong N.P., Clark T. et al. (2021). Recognizing the value of software: a software citation guide [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]. *F1000Research* 9:1257. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.26932.2>.
- Stall, S., Bilder, G., Cannon, M. et al. (2023). Journal Production Guidance for Software and Data Citations. *Sci Data* 10, 656. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02491-7>.
- Starr J., Castro E., Crosas M., Dumontier M., Downs R.R., Duerr R., Haak L.L., Haendel M., Herman I., Hodson S., Hourclé J., Kratz J.E., Lin J., Nielsen L.H., Nurnberger A., Proell S., Rauber A., Sacchi S., Smith A., Taylor M., Clark T. (2015). Achieving human and machine accessibility of cited data in scholarly publications. *PeerJ Computer Science* 1:e1. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1>.